

Using Flipped Classes to Develop Scientific Communication and the Attitude towards Technology Acceptance in Science Learning among Intermediate School Students

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Abstract

This study aimed for using flipped classroom learning to develop scientific communication and the attitude towards technology acceptance in science learning among intermediate school students. For this purpose, the quasi-experimental design with the experimental and the control group method was used. The sample involved (49)third intermediate stage students from Al-Khamaseen Intermediate School 2 and Al-Ladam Intermediate School 1, in Wadi Al-Dawasir Governorate, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. A list of written scientific communication levels suitable for intermediate school students and a procedural model for learning with flipped classes were presented. The study applied the scientific communication test and the technology acceptance in the science learning scale. The statistical analyses revealed that there were statistically significant differences between the means of the scores of the experimental and control group students in the scientific communication scale and the technology acceptance in the science learning scale in favor of the experimental group. Recommendations and suggestions were presented.

Introduction

Communication is a significant component in teaching as it reflects the process of interaction between the teacher and the learner. Besides, language plays an essential role in achieving this communication as it is a mediator for thinking that is used to convert observations into ideas. Developing a learner's communication skills helps him to express his ideas and opinions, formulating them to convey ideas and information to others. Therefore, it should be developed to achieve effective learning.

Communication is also an essential part of scientific practices. It is stated that it has become a basis for scientific knowledge in both scientific studies and science education. However, it is a negligent component that must be treated as a central component of science nature without which there would be no science. Mainly, it has a role in gathering facts and theories, and it is a resource for preserving, making, and expanding the scope of knowledge (Nielsen, 2013). Scientific communication means striving to create knowledge, acquire information, share ideas with others, and coexists with scientific changes (Muslim, 2011). Many scientific education studies have been concerned with developing scientific communication through utilizing various strategies and all of them have demonstrated the effectiveness of different strategies in its development. (Salem, 2001; Al Sayed, 2010; Kolber, 2011; Muslim, 2011; Rizk, 2014; Kirsh, 2015).

Developing learners' scientific communication is one of the main objectives that must be focused on to be aware of the language of science. The more opportunities are provided to the learner to integrate him into effective educational activities, and the more he deals with vocabulary, formulas, and scientific symbols, the more his ability to explore the meanings and connotations of the scientific concepts and structures that he deals with (Salem, 2001).

Today, human society lives in the era of the technological revolution associated with advanced information technology. Within the framework of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia's interest in e-learning, all schools in the Kingdom will transform into an interactive digital environment, and paper textbooks will be disposed of as soon as possible (Ministry of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, 2017). Consequently, there is a need to use teaching models that employ technology, such as flipped classroom learning that is concerned with technological applications in teaching and learning.

Flipped classroom (FC) is a contemporary method that concentrates on taking the advantage of technology to activate students' participation and interaction. This method provides learners with opportunities to communicate with the teacher and to create a kind of learning ownership because they feel responsible for their learning (AlJaser, 2017). Learning in the flipped classroom helps learners greatly to communicate because students do homework and assignments after completing presentations outside the classroom. Students also may

be asked to write a report and a summary of what they have been learned, and thus helps in developing scientific writing skills and their ability to communicate (Deri, Mills, & McGregor, 2018).

Many studies have concentrated on learning in the flipped classroom in science education to develop achievement, maintain the impact of learning, and discuss students' perceptions about it (Jeong, González-Gómez, & Cañada-Cañada, 2016). Also, Akkaraju(2016) used it for developing self-regulation and reducing the cognitive load in biological. Other studies concentrated on investigating the effectiveness of using FC on developing biology achievement (Heyborne& Perrett, 2016;Leo&Puzio, 2016;Son, 2016; Akkaraju, 2016). Moreover, Ramlo(2015) used it in physics education, while Liou, Bhagat& Chang(2016) used it in teaching science in general, and Deri, Mills& McGregor(2018)in general chemistry.

Reviewing the literature on the role of the learner in e-learning and blended environments showed that the learner is the most important factor that must be taken into account when developing such environments. Hence, the learner's positive attitudes and acceptance of new technology is a major factor in the success of flipped classroom learning (Al-Farih& Al-Kandari, 2014). This attitude is formed before the age of 14 years.The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) revealed that there is a decrease in the number of students in the field of science and technology, and this is evidenced by the reluctance of students to enroll in programs that integrate science and technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) due to the weak acceptance of technology (Ardies, Maeyer, Gijbels&Keulen, 2015).

In this context, Davis introduced the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) to predict and justify the level of technology acceptance within learning environments. This model indicates how perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use affect acceptance of new technology (Davis, 1989; Davis, 1993). Accordingly, developing technology acceptance is a necessary process for qualitative improvement in education, as the learners' acceptance determines when and how it will be used in the classroom (Govender, 2012). Acceptance of technology in science learning implies behavioral patterns that can be acquired and modified through learning and experience; these patterns are subjected to the principles and regulations that govern other patterns of behavior. Nevertheless, developing positive attitudes towards technology use raises the learners' interest and knowledge about it and how to benefit from it in the current era.

The technology acceptance model is one of the most popular models that has been used and is still being used until now in examining the extent of technology acceptance. Several studies have used it mainly in the field of blended learning and e-learning management systems (Al-Saidi, 2015; Al-Farih&Al-Kandari, 2014; Al-Azawei, Parslow& Lundqvist, 2017; Yeou, 2016).

Based on what was mentioned above and from the results of the pilot study conducted by the researcher, the significance of scientific communication and its' development is clear, and that learning in flipped classes is one of the modern methods that can be employed for developing scientific communication as it increases students' awareness of his effective role in his learning by following the lessons by himself before coming to the classroom, while the teacher evaluating and discussing him about what he learned, presenting it to peers. Besides, the study highlights the need to concentrate on the acceptance of technology in science learning as a product of learning in the flipped classes that it is concerned with the application of technology in learning and as one of the important aspects of keeping pace with the increasing technological developments in this era. Hence, the current study seeks for using flipped classroom learning to develop scientific communication and the attitude towards technology acceptance in science learning among intermediate school students

Hypotheses

1. There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the mean scores of the control and experimental groups in the written scientific communication test in favor of the experimental group.
2. There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the mean scores of the control and experimental groups in the technology acceptance in science learning scale in favor of the experimental group.

Significance

This study is up to date in terms of the fact that it concentrates on flipped learning, which has become a necessity in recent years in various educational levels. According to the researchers' knowledge, there are few studies concerned with the TAM in academic courses, except the study of Önal(2017) in learning mathematics and Sabti&Chaichan (2014) in learning English, but there is no study in learning science. The significance of the current study stems from providing a guide for intermediate school science teachers to apply learning in flipped classes procedurally, the written scientific communication test, and accepting technology in science learning scale, which helps them to measure such aspects and work on their development. The study also directs the attention of intermediate school science curriculum planners and developers to the necessity of adopting the use of flipped classroom learning in science teaching, paying attention to developing scientific communication, and accepting technology in science learning. This study is expected to provide suggestions for further researchers and helpful measurement tools.

Methods

Type of the study

This study is designed in the quasi-experimental design with the experimental and control group, which is the frequently used model in the educational field that aims to establish a cause-and-effect relationship between an independent and dependent variable.

Study Group

The study group comprised (49) third intermediate grade students of Al-Khamaseen Intermediate School 2 and Al-Ladam Intermediate School 1 in Wadi Al-Dawasir Governorate, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, the program was applied in the academic year 2017-2018. This group was divided into the experimental group (26) who taught with the flipped classroom and the control group (23) taught with the conventional teaching method. A random sampling technique was used to select the sample who would participate in the flipped classroom program.

Study Procedures

Preparing the written scientific communication dimensions list suitable for the third intermediate grade

The list aimed to determine the appropriate scientific communication skills for the third intermediate grade students. After reviewing related literature, studies, and measures accessible in this variable (Salem, 2001; Spektor-Levy, Eylon & Scherz, 2009; Muslim, 2011; Rizk, 2014), six levels of written scientific communication have been identified, namely: the level of the vocabulary, the sentence, the paragraph, the essay, the written expression, and the representation.

The list was presented in its initial form to suitable experts to determine the suitability of the dimensions. The dimensions that obtained more than (90%) agreement were taken, and through that, five levels of written communication were reached, which are as follows:

1. The level of the scientific vocabulary: It is the correct use of the scientific word, which is composed of some alphabet and indicates a partial meaning.
2. The level of the scientific sentence: It is the correct use of the scientific sentence, which consists of two or more words, and has a useful meaning.
3. The scientific paragraph level: It is the correct use of the scientific paragraph that is composed of two sentences or a group of adjacent scientific sentences indicating a complex meaning of partial meanings.
4. Expression level: It is the ability to write freely in a correct scientific language and to organize ideas well scientifically.
5. Representation: It is the translation of scientific texts into other verbal formulas, the conversion of scientific drawings and images into scientific words, and the conversion of scientific texts into drawings, diagrams, and illustrations. This can be defined as follows:
 - Translating scientific texts into a new scientific formula: It is the process of converting scientific texts that revolve around a specific idea into another textual formula and does not violate the basic meaning of the text.
 - Converting scientific drawings and pictures into scientific words: It is the process of converting scientific drawings and pictures that revolve around a specific idea into a text format that includes all the meanings of the image.
 - Transforming scientific texts into drawings, diagrams, and illustrations: It is the process of converting scientific ideas into drawings, diagrams, or illustrations that include the basic idea presented by the scientific text.

Preparing the procedural model for learning using flipped classes in science

After reviewing related literature, studies, and measures accessible in using flipped classes in science (Al-Kuhaili, 2015; Hassan, 2015; Al-Shalabi, 2017), the procedural model was developed. The procedural model was presented to the arbitrators to show the extent of the integration and continuity of the stages of the procedural model for teaching in flipped classes in science, and some modifications were made.

Thus, the study reached a procedural model for learning using flipped classes in science as follows:

1. The learning stage outside the classroom: It is a stage that takes place in partnership between the teacher and the learner asynchronously. It is concerned with individual learning, and the teacher prepares for it in a planned manner. This stage includes two steps:
 - Activation: In it, students are prepared and their thinking about the lesson topic is stimulated. The presentation in this step focuses on attracting students' attention and presenting the most important main points that will be covered in the lesson.
 - Presenting learning materials and achieving goals: where the points included in the lesson are widely displayed outside the classroom and this step includes:
 - Introducing each of the main points of the lesson interestingly and attractively.
 - Uploading video clips, which should be short (not exceeding 10 minutes) focusing mainly on the content of the lesson, and some illustrations can be uploaded related to each of the points covered by the lesson.

- Some short questions were asked about the scienceto test the learners' extent of familiarity with what was presented. These questions are related to each video or illustration.

- Inviting students to communicate with the teacher to discuss everything related to the lesson.
- The student writes a report on what he learned in the lesson in his own words and saves the report for presentation in the classroom.

2. Learning inside the classroom: This stage is inside the classroom focusing on ensuring the occurrence of learning. It mainly depends on students' discussion of what has been learned before coming to the classroom, and this stage includes two steps:

- Guidance and follow-up: in which the following is done:
 - Asking questions to ensure that students are ready, and to inform them of the learning material before coming to class.
 - Each student presents a report they wrote about what was learned in the lesson.
 - Evaluation: This includes:
 - The teacher distributes the worksheets to groups of students.
 - Discuss the students about the questions contained in the worksheets.
 - Directing students to follow-up mechanisms for the next lesson.

Data Collection Tools

The written scientific communication test

This test aims to measure the written scientific communication skill of the third intermediate grade students. The test in its initial form included (27) multiple-choice items. Each item followed by four choices and only one choice is correct. To verify the test validity and reliability the researcher conducted a pilot study on (27) students at the Second Al-Ladam Intermediate School, Wadi Al-Dawasir Governorate.

The test was consulted to evaluate its' suitability to the test objectives based on expert opinions. The items that received less than (90%) agreement were deleted and the necessary modifications were made in light of their opinions. Construct validity was verified by calculating the test internal consistency with its five levels as shown in table (1). The total time for applying the test was (55) minutes.

Table 1. *Correlation Coefficients of the Written Scientific Communication Test Five Dimensions with the Overall Score*

N	Test Dimensions	Correlation Coefficients
1	Scientific Vocabulary	**0.85
2	Scientific Sentence	**0.81
3	Scientific Paragraph	**0.87
4	Expression	**0.83
5	Representation	**0.81

All correlation coefficients of the test five dimensions with the overall score were significant at (0.05) and ranged from (0.81-0.87).

To confirm the test reliability Cronbach's Alpha was calculated. The reliability coefficients for vocabulary domain (0.81), Sentence domain (0.77), paragraph domain (0.80), expression domain (0.83), representation domain (0.79), and the whole test (0.84). All coefficients are good reliability coefficients.

Accordingly, the final test form consisted of (25) items distributed into five levels as illustrated in table 2.

Table2. *Scientific Communication Test Description*

Test levels	Total	Items Number
Scientific Vocabulary	5	3-4-5-6-22
Scientific Sentence	4	7-8-24-25
Scientific Paragraph	5	9-10-11-12-23
Expression	6	1-2-13-15-16
Representation	5	14-17-18-19-20-21
The Whole Test	25 items	

The Technology Acceptance in Science Learning Scale

This scale aims to measure technology acceptance among the third intermediate grade students. The scale in its initial form consisted of (25) statements distributed into three dimensions: the attitudes towards using technology in learning science, the expected benefit of learning science using technology, and the ease of learning science using technology. The scale involved positive and negative statements. The 5-point Likert scale was used for scoring from strongly agree to strongly disagree. To verify the scale validity and reliability the researcher conducted a pilot study on (27) students at the Second Al-Ladam Intermediate School, Wadi Al-Dawasir Governorate.

To ensure the scale face validity, the scale was consulted to evaluate its' suitability to scale objectives based on expert opinion. The statements that received less than (90%) agreement were deleted and the necessary modifications were made in light of their opinions. Construct validity was verified by calculating the scale internal consistency with its three dimensions as shown in table (3).

Table 3. Correlation Coefficients of the Scale Three Dimensions with the Overall Score

N	Test Dimensions	Correlation Coefficients
1	Attitudes towards using technology in science learning	*0.90
2	The expected benefit of learning science using technology	*0.85
3	The ease of learning science using technology	*0.83

All correlation coefficients of the scale three dimensions with the overall score were significant at (0.05) and ranged from (0.83-0.90).

To confirm the scale reliability Cronbach's Alpha was calculated. The reliability coefficients for the attitude dimension towards using technology in science was(0.83), the expected benefit of learning science using technology dimension (0.78), The ease of learning science using technology dimension (0.85), and the overall score (0.81). All coefficients are good reliability coefficients.

Accordingly, the final scale form consisted of (22) statements distributed into three domains as illustrated in table 4. They are as follows:

- Attitudes towards using technology in science learning: It is the result of the student's responses to what he thinks about the pleasure and passion, or opposition and boredom of technology in learning science.
- The expected benefit of learning science using technology: It is the outcome of the student's responses about what he thinks whether employing and applying technology in science learning will improve the performance of his learning tasks.
- The ease of learning science using technology: It is the outcome of the student's responses to what he thinks whether using technology in learning science will be with minimal effort.

Table4. The Technology Acceptance in Science Learning Scale

Scale Dimensions	Total Statement Number	Statement Numbers	Negative Statements	Positive Statements
Attitudes towards using technology in science learning	7	6-1	3-7	1-2-4-5-6
The expected benefit of learning science using technology	9	7-15	13-16	7-8-9-10-11-12-14-15-17
The ease of learning science using technology	6	13-23	23-19	18-20-21-22
The Whole Scale	23	6	17	

Preparing the Learning Material

Preparing the Teacher's Guide

The teacher's guide was prepared for the lessons of the third unit "chemical bonds and interactions," which included Chapter Five "Atomic Structure and Chemical Bonds" and Chapter Six "Chemical Interactions" according to learning in flipped classes. The guide included the introduction, general directions, steps for learning in flipped classes, an overview of scientific communication and the attitudes towards learning science using technology, downloading the Telegram program and the time plan required for teaching, and presenting lessons according to learning in flipped classes.

The flipped classroom learning platform

The Telegram was used as a platform to upload video clips, learning materials, and notifications to implement learning in flipped classes, and the researcher created a flipped classroom channel on the Telegram program, and all the experimental group students were provided with the channel link, which is:

<https://t.me/joinchat/AAAAAE749URflhushZypAQ>

FIGURE 1.A Screenshot of The Flipped Classroom Channel Showing the Videos Upload to Apply Flipped Classroom Learning

Preparing student book and worksheets

The student book was prepared including an introduction, general instructions for the student, a summary about learning in flipped classes, scientific communication, the attitudes towards learning science using technology, and downloading the Telegram program. The experimental group students were provided with the

channel link and a CD was distributed for the student to use if there is no internet connection. Then, unit lessons were presented using flipped classroom learning, and worksheets attached to each lesson were prepared.

Flipped classroom learning application procedures

The study tools were pre-applied to the control and the exponential groups. The equivalence of each of the two groups was checked in the written scientific communication test and the technology acceptance in science learning scale as indicated in table 5.

Table 5. *The Significance of Differences between the Means of the Scores of the Experimental and the Control Group in the Pre-Measurement*

Tool	Group	Number	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-value
The written scientific communication test	The experimental group	26	13.9	1.3	1.5
	The control group	23	13.2	1.7	
the technology acceptance in science learning scale	The experimental group	26	60.1	3.9	1.1
	The control group	23	63.3	3.4	

As table 7 illustrated there were no statistically significant differences between the means of the scores of the experimental and control groups, and thus confirms the equivalence of the two groups.

Then the researcher taught the assigned units for the experimental group using flipped classroom learning, while the control group taught traditionally. The study application lasted (14) sessions including the application of the study tools.

After applying the experimental treatment, the study tools were post-applied to the experimental and control groups. The results were monitored for statistical treatment to draw conclusions and make recommendations and suggestions.

RESULTS

In this part of the study, the data obtained in line with the study hypothesis.

Results Related to hypothesis 1 stating that "There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the mean scores of the control and experimental groups in the written scientific communication test in favor of the experimental group", to verify the validity of this hypothesis t-test was utilized and the following table indicated the results:

Table 6. *The Results of "t" Test and Its Significance for Differences between the Control and Experimental Groups in the Written Scientific Communication Test*

Domain	The Highest Degree	The Control Group		The Experimental Group		t-value	Significance Level	df	η^2
		Mean	St.dv	Mean	St.dv				
Vocabulary Level	5	2.0	1.1	3.9	0.8	7.2	0.05	47	1.8
Sentence Level	4	2.2	1.2	3.7	0.9	7.1			1.3
Paragraph Level	5	1.9	1.4	3.1	1.0	6.4			0.9
Expression Level	6	2.5	0.8	4.1	1.2	5.5			1.3
Representation Level	5	2.0	1.0	3.5	1.3	4.5			1.2
The Whole Test	25	10.1	4.2	18.6	3.9	7.4			2.0

From the previous table, it becomes clear that there are statistically significant differences between the experimental and control groups in the written scientific communication skills test and its five levels in favor of the experimental group, and that the effect size values ranged from (0.9- 2), and all are considered high values, so the first hypothesis is accepted for the study.

Results Related to hypothesis 2 stating that " There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the mean scores of the control and experimental groups in the technology acceptance in science learning scale in favor of the experimental group", to verify the validity of this hypothesis t-test was utilized and the following table indicated the results:

Table 7. The Results of "t" Test and Its Significance for Differences between the Control and Experimental Groups in the Technology Acceptance in Science Learning Scale

Domain	The Highest Degree	The Control Group		The Experimental Group		t-value	Significance Level	df	η^2
		Mean	St.dv	Mean	St.dv				
Attitudes towards using technology in science learning	30	10.3	3.7	25.4	3.4	14.5			4.1
The expected benefit of learning science using technology	45	22.6	6.2	33.8	4.6	7.0	0.05	47	1.8
The ease of learning science using technology	30	12.6	3.8	23.8	3.5	10.5			2.9
The Whole Scale	105	45.5	8.2	83.1	6.2	18.0			4.5

From the previous table, it becomes clear that there are statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha = 0.05$) between students of the control group and the experimental group in the scale of Technology Acceptance in Science Learning Scale and its three dimensions in favor of the experimental group, and that the effect size values ranged (1.8- 4.5), and all are considered high values, so the second hypothesis of the study is accepted.

Discussion And Conclusions

Technological and digital literacy are two of the most important subjects for students in today's schools. Students are already bombarded with digital information from the internet, social media, and countless apps on "smart" devices. Beyond the fact that technology is both a process and a result of science, technological developments provide useful tools in teaching science for all educational stages.

Results demonstrated that there were statistically significant differences between the experimental and control groups in the written scientific communication skills test and its five levels in favor of the experimental group and the effect size values ranged from (0.9- 2). This result is consistent with several studies regarding the possibility of using instructional strategies and models for the development of scientific communication (Salem, 2001; Al Sayed, 2010; Kolber, 2011; Rizk, 2014; Kirsh, 2015). It is also in line with Muslim's (2011) study results which stated the effectiveness of using educational blogs as one of the technological applications in learning via the Internet and flipped classroom learning depends on employing technology as well.

This result can be explained by the fact that learning in flipped classes helped to develop scientific written communication at the vocabulary level because students in the second step of the procedural model are interested in presenting learning materials and achieving goals in the first phase outside the classroom, followed by a set of short questions that are concerned with the basic scientific concepts contained in the videos that were shown in all the presented lessons. Besides, Students were asked to a write report that includes what they have learned in their own words without stereotyping their ideas in the second step of the procedural model, which is concerned with presenting the learning materials and achieving the prescribed objectives. The possibility of replaying the videos many times and learning at the speed that suits them helped to develop written communication at the sentence level, paragraph, and expression. All these factors allowed students to write in a correct and scientific language and to organize ideas scientifically.

Presenting learning materials in the form of various video clips and the use of illustrations in the presentation of lessons in the learning phase outside the classroom helped students to develop their written communication at the level of representation. Scientific information and concepts were displayed in the form of diagrams that closely manifest their shape in reality that could not be seen, such as atoms, and the types of chemical bonds, and not only that, but also the possibility for students to watch the videos several times and stop them whenever they wanted, helped them visualize and express these concepts in words, or translate those words into drawings and diagrams.

The procedural model of learning in flipped classes was concerned in the third step of the learning phase in the classroom by the students' presentations of what was learned through their self-reports that they wrote before coming to the classroom, it helped them to be accurate in their writings in a scientifically correct manner, which contributed to the development of written communication Levels.

Besides, results revealed that there are statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha = 0.05$) between students of the control group and the experimental group in the scale of Technology Acceptance in Science Learning Scale and its three dimensions in favor of the experimental group and that the effect size

values ranged (1.8- 4.5). This result is consistent with several studies regarding that blended learning helps the acceptance of technology, and flipped classroom learning falls under the umbrella of blended learning (Al-Saidi, 2015; Al-Farih& Al-Kandari, 2014; Al-Saidi, 2016; Al-Azawei, 2017; Yeou, 2016).

This result can be explained by the fact that learning with flipped classes helped to achieve fun in learning science, by moving away from stereotypes. Additionally, the students' use of the internet to watch the video clips made them motivated in learning science. Also, flipped classroom learning allowed students to learn outside of the classroom whereas means of comfort may be more available from learning in classrooms or laboratories, which helped to develop the dimension of enjoyment of learning science using technology.

Learning in flipped classrooms helped in simplifying information by displaying it visually using video clips, achieving students' self-reliance in learning, having learning materials before coming to the classroom, doing activities and assignments on their own, allowing them to review what was learned inside the classroom, and providing an opportunity for effective communication with the teacher and with all students in the classroom. Consequently, this was reflected in the development of the dimension of the expected benefit of learning science using technology. Learning in flipped classes was interested in providing learning materials in a form of video clips for learners. The procedural model relied on using Telegram, which is an easy and simple application for communication, sending video clips, and creating closed educational channels that helped to achieve the dimension of ease in learning science.

In light of the results presented and their interpretation, the study recommends the need for middle school science teachers to pay attention to the use of technology in teaching science, such as learning with flipped classes to develop scientific communication and accepting technology in science learning. Science curriculum planners and developers should also pay attention to using flipped classroom learning in organizing the content for science and planning teachers' guide. Furthermore, professional development program stakeholders should provide training courses for science in-service teachers on flipped classroom learning, methods of developing scientific communication, and accepting technology in science learning.

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